

Science

A REVIEW OF PAUSES AND SILENCE IN COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

Communication is very significant in any language for sharing ideas, thoughts and feelings. Though it is widely taught as an education discipline world over but, it doesn't have same form and style in all the places and life of persons. Through this research paper, we are describing the different perspective of communication and their significance. In the organizations, it is called as the base of business and in normal life; it is the medium of sharing our feeling. Whether we are from different regions, know different languages but the act of communicate enable us to understands each other. Its style may vary in men and women but it is equally important for both of them. Without communication we can't even think of our existence. It is a medium of exploring the world. It has strong power of healing the wounds of heart. Soft speakers are always welcomed by all. Through the best communication skills, one can reach the heights of success. It is the power of a leader. The main aim of writing this research paper on communication is to introducing the communication as a best device and with good communication we can win in every field.

Keywords: Communication; Education; Organization; Leadership; Silence.

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1. Introduction

According to James Thurber, "*Precision of communication is important, more important than ever, in our era of hair trigger balances, when a false or misunderstood word may create as much disaster as a sudden thoughtless act*" (Leadershipnow). Communication is an aspect of all systems. It is a glue which holds the elements together to form a system. Communication is something which we all do naturally day by day (W. Lambert Gardiner, 2008). Communication is an act of will directed towards a living entity that reacts (Garcia, 2012). Communication is the

speaking skills that either forms an image of us as a change agent, reliable and sturdy employee or a frail, requiring supervision worker. A good communication has no alternative. (Pappas, 2017). A conversational speech is actually a series of words punctuated by verbalized pauses, hesitation, and interruptions from other participants in the conversation (Collins, 2009). Successful communication is a prerequisite of effective transfer of knowledge. (Gitimu, 2005). "Communication is the vehicle which allows humans to recall the past, think in the present and plan for the future." (Shwewyn P. Morreale, 2000) Although Elbert Hubbard said "The only way to learn to speak is to speak and speak, and speak and speak, and speak and speak and speak," (Tracy) "Reckless words pierce like a sword, but the tongue of the wise brings healing" (Hanes). Communicating our thoughts and ideas is beneficial to us as well as others (Paul, 2010). Communication, the exchange of information or ideas between sender and receiver, is a challenging aspect in your personal life, at school, and especially in selling. (Richmond, 2010). Be mindful of our body language. Tony Robbins saying, "Motion creates emotion." How we move influences how we feel, and thus how you communicate. Flexibility is power. Being flexible means going with the flow. If we encounter resistance in a conversation, simply change your approach. In communication, calculated pauses are just as important as choosing words wisely. When we speak, give others and the universe an opportunity to respond, while you listen and observe (Niurka, 2013). Aristotle identified the three critical elements-ethos, pathos, and logos. Ethos is essentially our credibility — that is, the reason people should believe what we're saying.. Pathos is making an emotional connection — essentially, the reason people believe that what we're saying will matter to them. Logos is our mode for appealing to others' sense of reason, ergo the term logic. While some people can get by on gut feel, as Steve Jobs famously tried to convince us he did, most leaders are required to provide some kind of analysis to make clear their decisions. Effective leaders know the effort and time spent making explicit the connections they're drawing from the data to the analysis to their conclusion are well worth it. These three elements of communication reinforce one another. We may rely heavily on data and analysis (logos) to make a point and in so doing create a perception of expertise and authority on a topic (ethos). And while all three are necessary to excellent communication, improving our ability to do any one of them will help us become a better communicator and so a better leader (Edinger, 2013). Communication has often been referred to as a soft skill, which includes other competencies such as social graces, personality traits, language abilities, and ability to work with other people (Richmond, 2010).

1.1. Effective Communication

Effective communication is intentional. It is goal oriented. It is strategic. Unlike ineffective communication, effective communication is not impulsive or top-of-mind. It is not self-indulgent. And communication is not just about what one says. It is about anything one does or is observed doing. It is about any engagement with a stakeholder, including silence, inaction and action. Effective communication is hard. It requires discipline. It requires understanding the desired reaction among the group to which one communicates, which in turn requires knowing all well can about that group (Garcia, 2012). Truly effective communication enables an audience to focus on the message (Collins, 2009). Socially effective individuals, who are able to accomplish their objectives, believe that they are in control of social and cultural forces. Whether or not their belief is an illusion, their perception shapes their behaviour. The ethnographer as rhetorician provides a model of effective communication. Language is a powerful force that can

shape thoughts and influence minds. The rhetorician wants an audience to understand a particular message in a certain way. Therefore, the rhetorician shapes each presentation to the specific listeners who constitute the audience. The rhetorician designs each speech, each written expression, with this guiding image and audience in the mind. Thus an effective ethnographer is an effective communicator. Just as the absence of language requires thought and judgment, the use of literary conventions to communicate insights requires careful thought and judgement (Fetterman, 2014).

1.2. Significance of Communication

- 1) Communication enhances relationships to the self, others, and society, and is therefore central to general education.
- 2) Communication education Improves critical thinking.
- 3) Communication education helps students become more critical consumers of modern media.
- 4) Communication education develops leadership skills.
- 5) One must understand communication dynamics to build a successful family.
- 6) Communication education helps develop skills and sensitivities that shape our social and political lives.
- 7) Communication education can enhance cross-cultural understanding.
- 8) Communication education can help students gain a desirable job.
- 9) Oral communication and listening abilities are among the basic job skills desired by employers.
- 10) Communication education can increase upward mobility in one's career.
- 11) Communication education helps make business/customer interactions more satisfying and productive.
- 12) Communication education enhances the effectiveness of business executives.
- 13) Communication skills are top priorities for entrepreneurs.
- 14) Communication is a research discipline of emerging importance (Shwewyn P. Morreale, 2000).

1.3. Literature Review

If we desire to communicate effectively with someone, it is essential to honour his or her map of the world, regardless of whether or not we agree. This allows us to gather information and more easily understand their perspective, which will ultimately support us in creating consistent win win agreements (Niurka, 2013). Trust influences organizational processes such as communication, cooperation, and information sharing, and it affects productivity. Trust is a basic element of functioning relationships in organizations. Mental wellbeing is largely sustained by emotional support such as appreciation, respect, openness, and feedback. This can only possible through true communication (Hakkinen, March 2011). The fundamental battle being fought in society is the battle over the minds of the people. The way people think determines the fate of norms and values on which societies are constructed because communication, and particularly socialized communication, the one that exists in the public realm, provides the support for the social production of meaning, the battle of the human mind is largely played out in the processes of communication (Castells, 2007). Structures such as the wheel tended to have a more

hierarchical structure, with the central members receiving more leadership nominations and having more control over the decisions made by the group. In contrast, structures such as comcon had flatter hierarchies with a more equal distribution of leadership nominations. Sometimes more centralized communication structures led to higher performance than less centralized communication structures, and sometimes to lower performance (Cameron Anderson, 2010). In sectors such as service jobs that heavily rely on direct communication and contact with customers, communication skills are highly valued and extremely important. Therefore, women are more likely to be hired in these positions because they are, by nature of their communication style, more qualified than men for these jobs. Women tend to be more expressive, tentative, polite, social, while men are, on average, more assertive and dominant when it comes to communication style. Popular research has also shown gender differences in communication styles, from men being primarily goal-oriented and result-focused and women being relationship-oriented and placing a high value on closeness and intimacy in interactions with other people. This also points out common mistakes men and women make when conversing with each other, specifically focusing on gender differences in crisis communication (Merchant, 2012). "Communication exists within the family as a dynamic and essential force in the maintenance of relationships, and facilitates the development of the satisfied and healthy family." (Shwewyn P. Morreale, 2000)

2. Communication in Leadership

Leaders should be trained in group processing and facilitating skills, oral and written communication, conflict management, shared decision making, and team management. The four V leadership model incorporates all of these crucial elements in leadership development: values, vision, voice, virtue. The ability to communicate and accomplish goals, or the 'voice' element, is taught through exercises developing both interpersonal and intergroup communication skills, and utilizes mentoring and role-models to help leadership development."(Shwewyn P. Morreale, 2000). The fundamental battle being fought in society is the battle over the minds of the people. The way people think determines the fate of norms and values on which societies are constructed. Communication, and particularly socialized communication, the one that exists in the public realm, provides the support for the social production of meaning, the battle of the human mind is largely played out in the processes of communication. Politics is based on socialized communication, on the capacity to influence people's minds. The main channel of communication between the political system and citizens is the mass media system, first of all television (Castells, 2007). Communication is a learned skill, just like riding a bike. The more you practice, the better you become. And effective communication is about more than just talking: it's about listening, ensuring others get your point, and persuading others to take action on what you're saying. It's a simple fact: the most successful people in the world are also the best communicators. Our ability to communicate clearly and confidently accounts for 85% of our career or business success. We use public speaking every day – whether you realize it or not, people are listening and evaluating us, based on our ability to speak effectively (Tracy). Today, it's even more complex with business being conducted around the world and with varying communication methods the way in which we communicate can determine the level of trust that our colleagues or customers have in us. Creating our message is only half of communication; Listening is the other half. But it's difficult to listen because we listen faster than we speak—that

is, based on what the other person is saying, we are already constructing responses in our minds before they have even finished (Richmond, 2010).

Every leader has a vision. For Nelson Mandela, it was a South Africa without Apartheid. For Lech Walesa, it was a Poland run by workers and common people. For Susan B. Anthony, it was a United States in which women had the right to vote.

- 1) Communicating vision to others helps to decide to the direction in which direction we are headed in. If our vision is one that touches a chord with many people and if we can communicate it well, people will join us in reaching towards our goals. In the words of the Syracuse Cultural Workers, "No matter what our attempts to inform, it is our ability to inspire that will turn the tides."
- 2) Sharing a vision is a central role of a leader--a vision gives people a bigger picture of what things can be like. It helps people raise their hopes and expectations; it inspires them. When people are inspired, they are more likely to work on something.
- 3) A leader has to lead. And the most important aspect of leadership is winning over the thinking of people to a vision of what things can be like.
- 4) People who communicate a vision of what things should be like are often the people who are courageous enough to state what is obviously wrong and unjust (Axner, 2016).

2.1. Communication is a Discipline of Leadership

A leader is judged base on three fundamental public leadership attributes.

- 1) The leader's bearing: How the leaders carries himself or herself
- 2) The word that leader uses to engage others.
- 3) The manner in which the leader engages others.

These are the elements of communication. As a leadership discipline communication benefits from the structures, concepts, and principles of effective leadership in other fields (Garcia, 2012).

2.2. Trust in Leader's Communication

Employees that trust their leader work effectively and have a high level of commitment. In addition, they share ideas and knowledge, tacit knowledge in particular. Trust in the behaviour of other people grows when cooperation is reciprocated. Respect and appreciation stimulate the development of trust, while poor leadership underestimates employees' personal competences and this eventually results in declining work and company performance. Building trust is considered an essential activity in managerial leadership. However, the task of building and maintaining trust is complex. A leader's traits, behaviour, leadership style, and skills all matter in building trust and creating an impression of trustworthiness. So a leader should always speak truth and communicate correct information (Hakkinen, March 2011).

3. Communication in Business Organization

Communication is merely the continuation of business by other means. The goal of communication is not to communicate, but to accomplish some tangible business goals (Garcia, 2012). Two challenges are pervasive in the current business environment: The Curse of Emotion,

the fear of public speaking and the Curse of Knowledge –sharing too much information. Effective presentation training is essential in order to overcome them and connect to the hearts and minds of our audience (Novsky, 2016). It is widely accepted that business management and business educators perceive communication skills as highly valuable to employees and organizations alike. Over half of the heads of corporate communication departments oversee business communications functions that include media relations, online communications, marketing, special events, product/brand communications, crisis management, employee/internal communications, community relations, and product/brand advertising. The expanse and importance of business communication underscores the need for business education and business to collaborate in preparing business majors for the workplace (David Conrad, 2011).

3.1. Communication in the Organization's Hierarchy

Darwin's belief that hierarchies are necessary for groups to succeed pervades the social sciences. Hierarchies are a universal feature of all human groups, including organizations. Steeper hierarchies will harm collective success when the hierarchy impairs communication, trust, and coordination among group members. According to the functionalist perspective, hierarchies help groups solve each of these problems. Hierarchies are thought to help groups address the third major challenge, that of intra-group coordination, by reducing conflict and facilitating communication. Hierarchies are also thought to allow information to flow between members more efficiently and for the integration of this information to occur more easily. For example, in the prototypical pyramid hierarchy, information travels up through hierarchical levels until it reaches group leaders. The leaders integrate this diverse information and make the relevant decisions. Their decisions then flow down to each respective hierarchical level and get implemented according to leaders' plans (Cameron Anderson, 2010).

Organisational communication leads to stories, which are made and remade, and are combinations of "talk" in formal (e.g. meetings, public discourse) and informal (e.g. coffee breaks, sub-public discourse) settings. Language is regarded as a vehicle to construct meaning instead of a medium to transmit information. Hence, language is an essential part of individual and collective sense-making processes. Talks, conversations, and use of language are expressions of one's beliefs and reflect the social community to which one belongs. Discourse analysis of organisational change and resistance processes has been undertaken mostly from a "vertical", hierarchical perspective. Discourse problems also emerge in the horizontal dimension of interaction involving peer groups: For example, project team members of different departments that have to cooperate in implementing change projects. When people from different professional backgrounds interact, the same words might be interpreted differently; varying interpretations prohibit the development of shared mental models. Moreover, typically loyalty of professionals is geared towards their own colleagues who speak the same language and have the same mindset. This loyalty will cause professionals to orient themselves primarily on the discourse and language of their fellows, instead of members of other professional communities. The dynamics of not understanding each other's thoughts and discursive worlds can cause cooperative change efforts to break down, ending in frustrated professionals who refuse to take the interests of the others seriously (Jos H. Pieterse, 2012)

4. Communication in Cultural Context of Business

Communication is fundamental in business, because business is a collaborative activity. Goods and services are created and exchanged through the close coordination of many persons, sometimes within a single village, and sometimes across global distances. Coordination of this kind requires intense communication. Complex product specifications and production schedules must be mutually understood, and intricate deals between trading partners must be negotiated. Communication styles vary enormously around the world, and these contribute to a staggering variety of business styles. Business communications styles can differ markedly even among rule-based cultures, and similarly among relationship-based cultures.

- 1) The American speaker begins with a small joke to “break the ice,” while this is inappropriate in Germany. Germans wish to be reassured by the professionalism and seriousness of the speaker. The American’s slides contain flashy visuals with such phrases as “fantastic opportunity,” which strikes the Germans as childish. They prefer graphs and charts to reassure them that proper market research has been conducted. These differences are due to the fact that Germany is an uncertainty avoiding culture, while the United States is not.
- 2) It is true that the British are normally reserved and understated, while the French gave us the very word frank (which refers to the Franks, an old word for the French). Yet British can deliver a devastating comment with scarcely an inflection of the voice. If French and Italians become animated or emotional in a business meeting, one must bear in mind that Descartes was French and Galileo was Italian, and at the end of the day the decision is likely to reflect the logic and pragmatism of a Glaswegian.
- 3) The situation changes somewhat as one moves east. Russian society, for example, is essentially rule-based, but business partners may find it more important to feel comfortable with each other than to get the financials right.
- 4) In Confucian cultures, for example, one never utters a word or takes an action without calculating the effect on face. This is obviously important when dealing with superiors or colleagues, as when verbal disagreements are muted and indirect signals are used in negotiation.
- 5) Courtesy is integral to business relations throughout the Middle East. Arabic, Turkish, Farsi, and other Middle Eastern languages contain many resources for polite speech, and when speaking the languages one should take advantage of this. Above all, it is important to convey a message that one enjoys the company of one’s business partners.
- 6) Another distinctive form of group communication is found in the Japanese practice of consensus building for a policy decision. The practice is traditionally known as *nemawashi* (“going around the roots”), which refers to the practice of preparing a tree for transplant, much as one prepares an organization for a new policy. A memo would be circulated among members of the group, each of whom would contribute ideas and identify them with his stamp. The object is to accommodate everyone’s view and thereby maintain harmony. Consensus building through informal consultation remains an important process in the Japanese business world. Decisions in an organizational setting tend to evolve in the middle ranks and receive ratification by superiors, perhaps at a formal meeting. This is not a denial of high power distance but actually protects it, because if the decision turns out to be a mistake, it is impossible to hold a single decision maker responsible, and face is saved.

The key to cross-cultural business understands one's business partners well enough to make cultural adjustments. The choice of trade language is normally a matter of convenience, reflecting the competencies of the parties involved (Hooker, 2008).

4.1. Intercultural Aspect of Communication

The primary purpose of intercultural communication is to increase understanding of culturally mediated communication phenomena. The "culture specific" focuses on identifying the communication behaviors of a specific culture. A rich repertoire of verbal and nonverbal behaviors appropriate to the intercultural situation as well as affective capabilities to react sensitively to fellow communicators from other cultures is a necessity in education. Obstacles to effective intercultural communication include attitudes and dispositions, stereotyping, and ethnocentrism. The business sector is probably most affected with the issues of intercultural communication. Today with emergence of multi-national companies and global companies, it is unlikely to do business without communicating cross culturally. In order to successfully communicate cross culturally, knowledge and understanding of cultural factors such as values, attitudes, beliefs and behavior should be acquired. Effective cross-cultural communication in global economy provides pragmatic tools about how to define a communication strategy, train representatives and conduct business talks in order to achieve success. Interpersonal communication skills are essential to all helping relationships of cross-cultural counselling (Gitimu, 2005).

5. Communication Styles Differs in Men and Women

Conversation style differences frequently lead to women being evaluated as less competent than men. Women's (Venusians) sense of self in the work place is defined primarily by the quality of her work relationships. In the work place, Venusians respect efficiency and achievement, but values support, trust, and communication more. Venusians experience fulfilment by sharing, collaborating, and cooperating in the process of achieving greater success. Women often use tagged phrases like "don't you think" following the presentation of an idea, "if you don't mind" following a demand or "this may be a silly idea, but" preceding a suggestion. Women may perceive men's conversational dominance as an exercise of power. As a consequence, women who talk for more than one third of the available time may be regarded by others as talking too much (Ahmad, 2010). The most prominent leaders of the first wave of feminism in the United States are Lecretia Mott, Elizabeth Stanton, Lucy Stone, and Susan B. Anthony. Men and women differ psychologically in the way they act, from the style in which they communicate to the way in which they attempt to influence others.

- 1) The biggest difference between men and women and their style of communication boils down to the fact that men and women view the purpose of conversations differently. While women use communication as a tool to enhance social connections and create relationships, men use language to exert dominance and achieve tangible outcomes. Women are, overall, more expressive, tentative, and polite in conversation, while men are more assertive, and power-hungry.
- 2) Men view conversations as a way to establish and maintain status and dominance in relationships, women see the purpose of conversation to create and foster an intimate

bond with the other party by talking about topical problems and issues they are communally facing

- 3) Women are expected to use communication to enhance social connections and relationships, while men use language to enhance social dominance. On average, women use more expressive, tentative, and polite language than men do, especially in situations of conflict. Men, on the other hand, are viewed as more likely than to offer solutions to problems in order to avoid further seemingly unnecessary discussions of interpersonal problems.
- 4) Women, value cooperation, this communal orientation “involves a concern with others, selflessness, and a desire to be at one with others”. Females are also typically known to have a less clear focus on where the boundaries of their relationships end and their individual identities, defined in terms of relational bonds, begin. Females value talk for the relationships it creates; for females, the process of communication itself is valued. Women use less powerful speech: they tend to swear less, speak more politely, and use more tag questions and intensifiers.
- 5) Women are more social emotional in their interactions with others, whereas men are more independent and unemotional or attached in conversations. (Merchant, 2012).

6. Importance of Pause and Silence in Communication

We should use silence during our speech for emphasis. The effective use of silence is a powerful communications tool. Any bit of silence indicates that we are in charge and we want attention of the audience in the any conversation. The moment of silence will cause anyone not fully listening to refocus on us and will give greater impact to the phrase punctuated at either end by the silence. Silence can be a real booster of our authority, competence, and self-assurance. Shakespeare called the eyes “The mirror of the soul.” The eyes are a highly important communicator. The solution to sending the right signal with your eyes is simple and to the point: look at the person or people you are talking to (Collins, 2009).

Pauses are powerful and essential part of any presentation. A pause allows the listeners to make a personal connection to the word he or she just heard. A pause invites the listener to relax in to the presentation. A pause makes it possible for the speaker to sense the response of an audience to a presentation. Pauses are those beautiful moments when meaning happens and common ground emerges. Because many of us are afraid of pauses and silence, we tend to clutter them with speech- fillers. The ehms and OKs and you knows, the coughs, the giggles, heavy breaths, and the smacking of our lips. All the sounds we sneak in to our speech to banish the silence (Nowak, 2013).

- 1) Cultural factors such as country or region of origin and ethnic background influence how long a pause seems natural. For example, When Sally relocated from Texas to Washington, D.C., she kept searching for the right time to break in during staff meetings—and never found it. Although in Texas she was considered outgoing and confident, in Washington she was perceived as shy and retiring. Her boss even suggested she take an assertiveness training course. Thus slight differences in conversational style—in these cases, a few seconds of pause—can have a surprising impact on who gets heard and on the judgments, including psychological ones, that are made about people and their abilities (Tannen, 1995).

- 2) Every utterance functions on two levels. We're all familiar with the first one: Language communicates ideas. The second level is mostly invisible to us, but it plays a powerful role in communication. As a form of social behavior, language also negotiates relationships. Through ways of speaking, we signal and create the relative status of speakers and their level of rapport.
- 3) One way to judge confidence is by an individual's behavior, especially verbal behavior. Conversation is fundamentally ritual in the sense that we speak in ways our culture has conventionalized and expect certain types of responses. Men are more attuned than women to the potential face-losing aspect of asking questions. Ritualized way to start a conversation rather than a literal request for information. In other parts of the world, including the Philippines, people ask each other, "Where are you going?" when they meet. The question seems intrusive to Americans, who do not realize that it, too, is a ritual query to which the only expected reply is a vague "Over there."
- 4) Styles of giving feedback contain a ritual element that often is the cause for misunderstanding. Exchanging compliments is a common ritual, especially among women. Apologizing, mitigating criticism with praise, and exchanging compliments are rituals common among women that men often take literally. A ritual common among men that women often take literally is ritual opposition. Those who are uncomfortable with verbal opposition—women or men—run the risk of seeming insecure about their ideas.
- 5) Another linguistic signal that varies with power and status is indirectness—the tendency to say what we mean without spelling it out in so many word (Tannen, 1995).

In a real communication process, the message, the communicator and the truth conveyed through personality are much needed. The qualities of great personalities as a true speakers are many. Among them are faith, personal piety, unselfishness, magnetism, sociability, culture of the mind and heart, and devotion to humanity. The qualities most to be desired in the sermon as a speaker are clearness, logicalness, vivacity, earnestness, sweetness and light (Kleiser, 1908). A communicator can only empower, persuade and inspire others, only if he / she have the spark of enthusiasm, with humour, animation and he knows well the dynamics of communication. All these things make him/her a great communicator and improves the personality. It is in seclusion that the great communicators carefully craft that great public performance. The most important ingredient of a communication process is a focused purpose. Communication is about the people sitting in front of you. It's about giving to them, helping them, instructing them, and persuading them of something that will enrich their life (Davis, 2013).

7. Conclusion

We can say that communication is the essence of life. When people communicate with each other, they are not just sharing their feelings or describing their thoughts, but also maintaining a relation between each other. Although communication has many forms, from verbal to oral or form gestures to body language, but it has a certain identity everywhere. The way of speaking or the language may be different in all regions of world but it has a sense of belongingness which connects the world makes it a common place to live and share ideas to people. It has unique importance in every language of the world. The difference of communication style between men and women put a kind of variety in the communication process. It is the voice of leaders. Silence

can also be regarded as the best communication tool. So we can define communication as the most important identifier of language.

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